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BUILDING SECURITY, FOSTERING UNITY, SHARING VALUES: BULGARIA IN NATO FOR 20 YEARS

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NATO'S HUMAN SECURITY - 2024 AND HUMANITARIAN RESPONSE IN UKRAINE

Denitsa Hinkova

*"If we can't change the future,
then why waste time discussing it."
-Yuval N. Harari*

Abstract

The article highlights key areas of actions and reflects upon the main prospects for support, outlined by the Human Security Agenda (2024) for the assistance, relief and future recovery of Ukraine. The underlying hypothesis addresses the opportunities for Bulgaria to build upon and enhance its defence capabilities, resilience capacity and preparedness for crisis management and disaster risk reduction, abiding to the priorities in the HS Agenda and though more active participation in the capability coalitions in Ukraine. The paper identifies the options for positive outcomes in the future Bulgarian engagement with the capabilities of Ukraine and missions, in adherence to the core principles of NATO Human Security Agenda and the recommendations of new policy documents. The analysis provides recommendations to bridge the gaps in the contribution of Bulgaria in the joint engagements for the security of Ukraine, towards the horizon of 2025-2027. The main focus is on the ongoing missions, the Ukrainian Compact with joint humanitarian response, coordinated by UN-OCHA, European Union (ERCC) and NATO (EADRCC).

Keywords: *NATO, human security, preparedness, capacity, resilience, Bulgaria, Ukraine*

Introduction

Dedication to humanity is the sigh of hope that preserves solidarity in hardships, as a moral compass to the ideal of peace. In turbulent times, it reminds us of the enduring power of people that make a difference to save others, thus saving humanity. For young volunteers and humanitarian workers in Ukraine, like Anna Savenets in Dnipro - an IOM Field Operations Assistant, dedication is the mission to preserve the community and deliver day-by-day help to vulnerable people, enlightened with "*état d'esprit*" - the *spirit* of humanity. In a world of extremes and dynamic disruptions, more that ever before this "*spirit signifies being conscious of belonging to a cultural family and to have a willingness to serve that community in the spirit of total mutuality, without any hidden motives of hegemony*" (Schuman, 1949). Entrusted with the belief of shared common values and strategic culture, the 32 member states of NATO have

adopted a more enhanced approach to human security in the year of its 75th Anniversary, reaffirming that “*security is a shared responsibility that requires cooperation and collaboration between states and other actors*” (NATO, 2024). In response to the increasing global uncertainty, escalation of violence and instability along the “arc of fragility”, the Alliance to be integrated human security in its defense and deterrence policy and underscored its adherence to the international humanitarian law and three core principles of human security that are: “*freedom from fear, freedom from want, and freedom to live in dignity*” (Annan, 2005). The ontology of human security from theory to practice in the 21st C. provides evidences on the evolution of the term from the “awareness of the anomaly” (Kuhn, 2012) – the problem of structural violence (Galtung, 1969) towards the through a paradigm shift as a “*fundamental change in the understanding, when earlier assumptions are disproven*” (Kuhn, 2012) in the field, towards a “*new security framework that centers directly on people*” (Hampson et al., 2002, Launtensach, 2021). Scientific transformation has led to a deeper understanding of the decisive efforts of international community (Thakur, 2010), not only to preserve the human rights and promote multilateralism, based on the international humanitarian law, but also to safeguard the “*shielding of people from acute threats and empowering people to take charge of their own lives*” (Ogata, Sen, 2003). In nearly 30 years of development of human security concept, since the HD Report (UNDP, 1994), scholarly contributions developed methodologies, tools, metrics and indices, for policy implementation in the multiple domains of politics, sociality, economics, health and environment (Launtensach, 2006, Penny, 2007, Kaldor, 2010, Thakur, 2010; Pelling, 2010; Bendell, 2011; Hampson 2011, Raskin, 2016, Lautensach & Lautensach 2020). Since then, it has been critically accepted by some scholars as conceptually ambiguous or as an institutional mainstream (Newman, 2005), especially with reference to R2P, however its positive impact may be objectively verified though impact assessment of the missions in the humanitarian domains. The dynamics and uncertainty of an *international order in transition* (NATO, ACT 2024) international relations, demand positive actions in several vectors, including humanitarian action and empowered human networks, focused on peace and resilience towards a balance in a multipolar world, (fig. 1).(WEF, 2024).

with the Euro-Atlantic Disaster Response Coordination Centre – part of the Operations Division at NATO HQ and available 24/7 (EADRCC, 2024). Contributing to humanitarian relief and aid for over 100 emergencies around the globe, ever since 1998, the EARCC is the key mechanism to train, prepare capacity and respond to civil emergencies, natural and man-made disasters. It can also be activated during collective defence situations in the scope of Article 5 (EARCC-NATO, 2024). As a focal point of crisis and disaster management EARCC coordinates operations for international assistance, especially when emergency appeals are activated is in close collaboration with partner nations and organizations, mainly ERCC, EU and OCHA, UN; ICRC /IFRC-Red Cross, IAEA and other coordinating centers active 24/7. (fig2.)

Figure 2. EARCC coordination Clearing House mechanism. Source: NATO, 2024.

To enhance interoperability of member states, planning operations require coordination within important Planning Groups for humanitarian response in the field of: *Civil Communications, Civil Protection Energy, Planning Food and Agriculture, Joint Health and Transport area*. As well as, there are seven baseline requirements that integrate human security approach, accepted as critical for national resilience to measure the level of preparedness (table 1):

<i>NATO's Resilience - 7 Baseline Requirements</i>	
1	Continuity of government and critical government services (Decision-making and public communication)
2	Energy supplies: ensuring a continued supply of energy and having back-up plans to manage disruptions
3	Uncontrolled movement of people and to de-conflict movements from NATO's military deployments
4	Food and water resources - supplies that are safe from disruption or sabotage.
5	Mass casualties and disruptive health crises: civilian health systems, medical supplies, stocked & secure.
6	Civil communications systems- telecommunications and cyber networks under crisis conditions, back-up capacity, 5G, robust options to restore systems, priority access to national authorities.
7	Transport systems- ensuring rapid movement of NATO forces and transportation networks, even in a crisis

Table 1. Civil preparedness baseline requirements

The common understanding of members that *“human security is at the core of what NATO does and who NATO is”* (NATO, 2024), leads to collective efforts to build societal resilience and capacity for an *Article 5*-scenario and it provides meaningful context of the security environment (NATO, 2024). This policy framework has already been adopted by NATO as an outcome from the Wales Summit in 2014, resulting in practical cooperation between partners to counter common security threats (NATO, 2014). The common understanding of human security is enshrined as well in the Guiding Principles of Madrid Summit, 2022 (NATO, 2024). It entails measures for *“maintaining and developing national and collective capacity of societal*

resilience, to resist armed attack and to recover from shocks”, as a reinforcing area to human security (NATO, 2024). NATO HS Agenda 2024 is focusing on the inclusive approach of civil preparedness and the priority to safeguard people and build civil preparedness capacity in the area of three core tasks: 1. *continuity of government* 2. *continuity of essential services to the population* 3. *civil support to the military*. (fig.3).

Figure 3. Core tasks of Human Security of NATO

The practical implementation of *human security model of NATO*, relates to “risks and threats to populations, where the Alliance has deployed operations, missions or activities, and how to mitigate and respond to them” (NATO, 2024). The core principles underline the importance CIMIC collaboration in NATO’s actions to mitigate and reduce the impact violence and insecurity on civilian populations, in conflict zones of conducting operations and missions else it may be conducting activities. According to NATO’s 2022 Strategic Concept: “*Human security, including the protection of civilians and civilian harm mitigation, is central to crisis prevention and management*” (NATO, 2022). Its comprehensive integration into non-military crisis operations, enhance prevention-oriented efforts against conventional and non-conventional threads and hazards, towards a sustainable peace in partnership with international and non-governmental humanitarian organizations (NATO, 2024). The new dimensions of the policy after the Washington Summit in 2024, propose advanced integration of civilian planning into national and collective defence planning in peace, crisis and conflict and deepening of the engaged humanitarian aid responsibility and commitment of international partners - UN cluster of originations and the European Union (NATO, 2024).The practically-oriented policy of NATO, encompasses five mutually complementary areas (fig.4).

Figure 4. Policy areas of Human Security -NATO

EU 2024 Approach “Safer Together” and the Humanitarian Response to Ukraine

In the European perspective, humanitarian aid is a vital part of EU Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations policy for nearly 32 years, providing assistance ever since 1992 in over 110 countries, addressing the needs of millions (DG ECHO, 2024). The European Union is the greatest global donor of aid for vulnerable communities and humanitarian policy is greatly supported by EU citizens and volunteers. It is assessed as a positive contribution by EU to the work of UN Agencies and international NGOs in the main areas of action – nutrition, food, shelter, healthcare, water and sanitation (WASH), education and reaction in emergency situations. According to the standard Eurobarometer survey (Oct./Nov., 2024), the most important areas for EU priorities of action for the next 5 years, according to the European citizens, should be security and defence (33%), migration (29%) and climate (28%), (fig.5).

QB6ab. In your opinion, in which of the following areas should the EU take measures in the medium term, i.e. in the next five years?

Figure 5. EU priority actions - next 5 years, Eurobarometer, 2024.

The European citizens identify as the main concerns the war in Ukraine (31%), immigration (28%) and the international situation (22%). The humanitarian action for Ukraine is supported as important in the public opinion 87% of respondents (EU 27). Higher majority of EU respondents (79%) support the common defence and security policy, with support ranging from 87% in Lithuania, Luxembourg and the Netherlands to 57% in Malta, 64% in Ireland and 65% in Portugal. (Eurobarometer 102 -Oct./Nov. 2024), (fig.6)

QD2. The EU has taken a series of actions as a response to Russia's invasion of Ukraine. To what extent you agree or disagree with each of these actions taken?

Figure 6. EU priority actions - next 5 years, Eurobarometer, 2024.

The EU policy on resilience and preparedness are intertwined with those of regional and global partner countries, focusing on the cross-border dimension of threats and hazards. In order to promote an evidenced-based approach for the policy formulation and enhance the preparedness of EU citizens for complexity, a new framework of action has been adopted by the Commission in October 2024 “Safer Together”, in a comprehensive report by the EC Special Adviser to the President and former President of the Republic of Finland *Sauli Niinistö*, “in order to enhance the EU’s civilian and military preparedness and readiness for future crises” (EC, 2024). This is a landmark strategic document for the EU, enhancing CFSP and humanitarian response with several positive implications, focusing on the *preparedness-by-design* and proactive and cross-sectoral external action (Niinistö, 2024). The common task to strengthening “*mutual resilience*” and preparedness in an “*increasingly contested world*”, is the main international priority of shared among multilateral partners. The main actions to be undertaken by member states

require investing resources and efforts in the building capacities to reduce risks, prevent, withstand, respond and mitigate extreme events, health crises, hybrid attacks, cyber-threats, armed conflicts (Niinistö, 2024). The policy model is based on anticipatory governance and scenario-based risk assessments, to provide alternatives and better option to focus on vital immediate issues and geopolitical hotspots of primary importance for EU, involving EEAS. The report poposes a *whole-of-government* and *whole-of-society* approach to build civil capacity to resist future shocks and crises. The model is applying foresight analysis and futures planning to provide guidelines for riskl mitigation and assistance to vulnerable people (Niinistö, 2024).

NATO and Ukraine - Mission for Ukraine (NSATU)

In accordance with the UN Charter and under the provisions of the Washington NATO Summit (July, 2024) the NSATU Mission - *NATO Security Assistance and Training for Ukraine* will provide humanitarian response and military assistance to Ukraine. It is tasked to coordinate the delivery of military equipment and training to Ukraine from NATO member states and partners and *operate on the territory of NATO member states*, to support Ukraine's self-defense (NSATU, 2024). The main activities are planned under the mechanism of enhanced political consultations within NATO-Ukraine Council. For the future recovery of Ukraine, NSATU mission operates in cooperation with partners and ongoing initiatives of the European Peace Facility and the EUMAM, Ukraine Defense Contact Group, including the work of the Capability Coalitions (EADRCC-NATO, 2024). In of all activities, this mission integrates the firm position on response to the war in Ukraine, reaffirmed by political leaders, at the G7 meeting in 2024, to safeguard the “*freedom, sovereignty, independence and territorial integrity of Ukraine for as long as it takes*” (G7, 2024). Under EARCC coordination, the mission has facilitated the delivery of humanitarian aid to Ukraine - ambulances, mobile X-ray machines and ventilators, provided training for capacity-building of crisis management capabilities, paramedic training and medical evacuation operations from Ukraine (NATO, 2024).

EU Military Assistance Mission for Ukraine (EUMAM) and European Peace Facility

The most important strategic mission for the humanitarian response to Ukraine by the EU is the EUMAN – *EU Military Assistance Mission* in support of Ukraine (EUMAM, Ukraine), initiated in 2022. Its core tasks are *to strengthen the capacity* of the UAF to defend the territorial integrity of Ukraine within its internationally recognised borders and *to deter and respond to possible* future military offensives by Russia and other potential aggressors (EUMAM, 2024). As mentioned above, international partners and EUMAM share the collective responsibility and collaborate closely together in humanitarian aid and training support to the Ukrainian Armed Forces (UAF). During the first 10 months of 2024, more than 630 partnering humanitarian

organizations provided assistance to 7.7 million people across Ukraine, out of 8.5 million people in need targeted, including people affected by attacks, 2.4 IDPs, 1.6 returnees and 4.4 non-displaced, as well as newly displaced people (OCHA, 2024). There is a strict requirement for EUMAM that “all mission activities are located on EU soil”. Until 2024, the training modules and capabilities have been allocated from 24 EU Member States and they offer further humanitarian assistance by the “provision of equipment for lethal and non-lethal purposes to the UAF”, funded by European Peace Facility (EPF, 2024). The main training of capabilities primarily is focused on medical assistance, CBRN, demining, logistics and communication, maintenance and repair. EUMAM Ukraine has already trained 63000 Ukrainian UAF soldiers, or 10 brigades and it provides operational training, junior leadership training for battalions and brigades in collective manoeuvres and tactics up to battalion level and advice on the planning, preparation and conduct of live firing exercises. Until the winter of 2024/2025 the mission will train additionally 15000 troops, with total number of defense capabilities trained to 75000 by the end this year. Just recently on November 8, 2024, the Council of the European Union (EUCO) has extended for 2 years the mandate of the EUMAM, Ukraine until November 15 2026, allocating funds of nearly 409 million EUR (Nov.14, 2024 – Nov.15, 2026) (Council of EU, 2024). The funding and military equipment for the mission is allocated through the mechanism of the European Peace Facility, which is a flexible instrument for operations under the CFSP, to speed up defence industrial production in the EU under the relevant instruments of the EU defense ecosystem (EPF, 2024). Since the beginning of the Russian aggression, the EU and its Member States have mobilised almost *EUR 122 billion in support of Ukraine* and its people. The Ukraine Facility entered into force on 1 March 2024 providing up to *EUR 50 billion in predictable and flexible support for Ukraine for 2024-2027*, to support its recovery, reconstruction and modernisation, in line with its EU path. Of this amount, EUR 12.4 billion has already been allocated and disbursed, as next funding will be provided to the State budget on fulfilment of the Ukraine Plan for reforms and investment agenda for the country in next 12 months (European Commission, 2024). For the recently coming years, it is expected that EU defence planning will demand rebalancing in accordance military capabilities, civil preparedness, logistics and defense industry production in accordance with the pressing the needs of member-states vis-a-vis the war in Ukraine and the conflicts in the Middle East, as well as a more systemic approach to enhance the critical operational capacities (EPF, 2024).

Capability Coalitions and Ukraine Defense Contact Group (UDCG)

The Ukraine Defence Contact Group (UDCG), also known as the “*Ramstein Coalition*” (from the meeting in the Ramstein Air Base) has been established in 2022, has initiated capability coalitions with its partners as an alliance of 57 countries (NATO all 32, EU and 25 other

countries) sending military equipment and focusing on long-term perspective of defense planning and future military capability requirements, as well as battlefield operations support (US State Department, 2024). New cooperation frameworks for the development of a common capability aim to cooperate in the areas of procurement, acquisition, and maintenance of specific military equipment and ammunition. Such an approach also offers additional benefits to participating nations in the form of reduced common costs and increased interoperability (FEU Journal, 2024). Capability coalitions represent a very efficient and promising format of collective military cooperation, where partners look for ways to increase Kyiv's efficiency on the battlefield and cut common costs. These multilateral arrangements make it possible to avoid the lengthy bureaucratic procedures of international organisations and at the same time focus on areas where the participating states have sufficient capabilities, relevant defence industrial bases or technologies, and financial resources. In 2024 there are 8 capability coalitions for Ukraine: 1) Artillery Coalition –lead by USA and France; 2) Integrated Air Defense – lead by Germany and France; 3) Drones Coalition – lead by Latvia and Germany; 4) Armored Vehicles – lead by Poland, Germany and Italy; 5) IT Cyber Coalition – lead by Estonia and Luxemburg; 6) Air Force Coalition – lead by Denmark, USA and France; 7) Marine Security – lead by Great Britain and Norway and 8) Demining /Marine Clearance Coalition- lead by Lithuania.

Figure 8. Capability Coalitions for Ukraine, 2024. Source –Rasmussen Center

Some examples of the activities of the coalitions are presented below, based on online references and media publications in 2024.

The Marine Clearance or Demining Coalition is one of the most important ones, because data shows that Ukraine is the most heavily mine-contaminated state in the world. The Fact-based evidences from UN Human Rights Monitoring Mission in Ukraine (HRMMU) reveal that unexploded mines contamination in Ukraine has killed 360 people since February 2022 and

wounded 790. Mines not only imperil Ukrainian civilian population and the military but also agriculture – according to data from Tony Blair Institute, mine hazard causes the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of Ukraine fall by approx. USD 11.2 billion on a yearly basis (URMMU, 2024). Another quite important capability is the Artillery Coalition, launched January 2024 in Paris and lead by USA and France, which aims to enhance the UAF’s capacity and establish interoperability with NATO, comprising of 14 nations with “*advanced technological capabilities to manufacture cutting-edge artillery systems, munitions, artillery reconnaissance assets, unmanned targeting systems, and fire control systems*”. There are plans that by 2027, the Artillery Coalition will provide integrated capability training and equipment to UDF that ensure interoperability with NATO (Ministry of Defense Ukraine, 2024). The Marine Security Capability Coalition is lead by UK and Norway and has 13 participating states. Along with the Demining/ Marine Clearance Coalition both are essential for the mine countermeasures in the Black Sea Region-MCM. It is built around two vessels - *Cherkasy and Chernihiv Vessels* – two former UK Royal Navy (RN) minehunters, HM Ships Shoreham and Grimsby (Ministry of Defense Ukraine, 2024), which were transferred to Ukraine under the UK/Ukraine/Norway Maritime Capability Coalition (MCC) programme in 2023 (Naval News, 2024). Bulgaria may cooperate with partners of Romania and Türkiye, to Ukraine for the future security and defense of the Black Sea environment, so that the Ukrainian Navy could have the opportunity to integrate its MCM capability. In January 2024, these three countries established the Black Sea Mine Countermeasure Task Group (MCM Black Sea), reflecting NATO’s need for allies to establish regional (non-NATO) partnerships. In the war, the navy’s MCM activities have been crucial in keeping trade routes open, with over 4,000 ships having used Odesa to date. Still Türkiye has closed the Bosphorus/Dardanelles straits (*under the 1936 Montreux Convention*), which means that ships *Cherkasy* and *Chernihiv* cannot yet sail to their new home. Only vessels already “*homeported in the Black Sea*” can transit the straits when it is closed. Instead, Ukraine uses uncrewed underwater vehicles (UUVs) for Black Sea MCM tasks. Ukrainian Navy is developing its new mine counter-measures (MCM) capability that has demonstrated this capability during Exercise “*Sea Breeze’ 2024*” Exercise , taking place off Scotland between 26 June and 5 July and ending up in Varna, Bulgaria -August, 2024. (Naval News, 2024). The future development of capability coalitions in 2025 require greater political and financial support to integrate new participating states and more collective engagements with project for “joint defence investments, procurement, and adaptation of defence industry capacities to long-term defence planning” (FEU Journal, 2024).

Opportunities for Bulgarian capacity in humanitarian response in Ukraine

In the course of 20 years of active partnership in NATO Bulgarian contribution to collective defense and deterrence, peace and crisis operations reveals a long path of dedicated engagement in missions such as ISAF, Resolute Support and KFOR. The political support for joint international efforts to safeguard the security of Ukrainian people, to is of critical importance for Bulgaria to express its true dedication to be actively involved humanitarian short and long-term response to Ukraine. The official position of Bulgaria is that given the proximity of the war in Ukraine to Bulgarian borders and the importance of this conflict for the security of Europe, therefor the country reaffirms its engagement to international support for “*the independence, sovereignty and territorial integrity of Ukraine, within its internationally recognised borders*” (Council of Ministers, Bulgaria, 2024). In accordance with the statement of Bulgarian Delegation to the Washington Summit of NATO, 2024: “ Bulgaria firmly supports Ukraine in its just cause to defend its right to freedom and independence and free choice of its own security safeguards. A peace outcome of the war shall not be detrimental to Ukraine’s territorial integrity. Russia shall abide by international law.” In order to support this position with active engagement, Bulgarian institutions had to overcome the challenges of the political crisis in the country and the stagnating modernization of the military capabilities, beyond the polarization in society. The comprehensive humanitarian response of Bulgaria for Ukraine refugees and IDPs continues since 2022. In December 2023 the Bulgarian parliament has approved the delivery of defective, or surplus, surface-to-air missiles and portable anti-aircraft missile systems. It also overrode a Presidential veto on the provision of 100 armoured personnel carriers and instructed the Ministry of Defence to take the necessary measures to join the F-16 Air Force Coalition, including offering pilot training and the use of Bulgaria’s airspace. Bulgaria has signed the G7 Joint Declaration setting out long term security guarantees to Ukraine. Negotiations on that agreement were launched at the end of October 2024 (BTA, Bulgarian News Agency, 2024). In this respect, the Bulgarian Council of Ministers has approved a decision in October, 2024 for a security cooperation agreement between Bulgaria and Ukraine for specific bilateral arrangements between the two countries, to provide Ukraine with political and practical support and to join the Ukraine Compact for capability coalitions, operating since July, 2024, being initiated at the NATO Summit in Washington (Council of Minister, Bulgaria 2024). In 2024 Bulgaria participated and contributed to the Integrated Air and Missile Defence Capability Coalition in Ukraine. Bulgarian Armed Forces will participate since 2024 within the NATO Security Assistance and Training for Ukraine (NSATU), as the Bulgarian governmental decision from August 7, 2024 has authorised the participation of the Bulgarian military in the Alliance's initiative to train Ukrainian servicemen, corresponding to the efforts of other member states of the Alliance. During 2024 Bulgaria has also sent 50

soldiers for the EU Military Assistance Mission in support of Ukraine (EUMAM Ukraine), which was trained Ukrainian troops (BTA, 2024). A recent decision by NATO-EADRCC confirmed forthcoming Bulgarian participation in a joint resilience-building exercise, that will bring together Allies and partners, as well as other international organizations. Participants will be confronted with scenarios that include natural and industrial disasters, hybrid threats, and complex emergencies. They will be able to test procedures related to the coordination of different activities and logistical support. This is essential to building resilience and to preparing for potential challenges, including those related to climate change (EADRCC, 2024).

Conclusion

As a manifest to the next generations for a peaceful future, the leadership of NATO initiated Human Security Agenda 2024, to advance further the bold vision to mobilise solidarity, strengthen community resilience and enhance humanitarian engagement. The advanced model of human security till next horizon - 2030, is incorporated as well in recent strategic frameworks and policy implications of partner international institutions – UN (Pact to the Future, 2024) and EU (Safer Together, 2024). Its purpose is not only to raise global awareness, but moreover to increase capabilities in a wider network for decisive humanitarian response in times of war and for post-conflict reconstruction. In the year of its 75th Anniversary, NATO maintains its commitment to human security and is dedicated to advancing its efforts in this area. The Alliance recognises the importance of setting standards on human security for its Allies and partners, as well as the dedicated responsibility for humanitarian response to Ukraine, as this crucial “*steadfast support*” has been reaffirmed by the words of NATO Secretary-General Mark Rutte in Brussels, 2024 (VOA, 2024). NATO will continue to explore the nexus between human security and all areas of work, including in emerging domains, as this process entails future aligning of policy areas, doctrine and guidance, so that member states build resilience and address future security challenges (Niinistö, 2024). Beyond the reflections of the frescoes of Francisco Goya’s “*Los Caprichos*”, we may perceive the spirit of our times, but not through violence, rather than through visions of enlightened reason to be reborn. Hopes for the positive tipping points in the near future reveal the demand for a more comprehensive, people-centered capacity-building and preparedness of citizens, implemented in the deterrence and defence approach and ongoing mission for humanitarian response.

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